

TRIBONACCI PRODUCT CORDIAL LABELING ON SOME BASIC GRAPHS

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Abstract

Bala et.al., discussed the concept of Tribonacci Product Cordial Labeling [1]. An injective function $\delta : R(G) \rightarrow \{T_1, T_2, \dots, T_m\}$ is said to be Tribonacci product cordial labelling if the induced function $\delta^* : B(G) \rightarrow \{0,1\}$ defined by $\delta^*(r_i r_j) = (\delta(r_i)\delta(r_j)) \pmod{2}$ satisfies the condition $|b_{\delta^*}(0) - b_{\delta^*}(1)| \leq 1$. A graph which admits Tribonacci Product cordial labelling is called Tribonacci product cordial graph. In this paper we investigate the existence of Tribonacci product cordial labelling for Wheel related graphs.

Keywords: Graph Labeling, Tribonacci Labeling, Cordial Labeling, Tribonacci Product Cordial Labeling.

1. INTRODUCTION

In 1967, Rosa [7] introduced the concept of graph labeling. Graph Labeling is an assignment of integers to the vertices or edges or both subject to certain condition.

Tessymol Abraham et.al., [11] discussed the concept of Fibonacci product Cordial Labeling, An injective function $f : V(G) \rightarrow \{F_1, F_2, \dots, F_m\}$, where F_j is the j^{th} Fibonacci number ($j = 1, 2, \dots, n$), is said to be Fibonacci product Cordial Labeling if the induced function f' from the edge set E of graph G to the set $\{0,1\}$ defined by $f'(uv) = (f(u)f(v)) \pmod{2}$ satisfies the condition $|E_{f'}(0) - E_{f'}(1)| \leq 1$, where $E_{f'}(0)$ is the number of edges with label 0 and $E_{f'}(1)$ is the number of edges with label 1.

A graph which admits Fibonacci product Cordial Labeling is called Fibonacci product Cordial graph.

Bala et.al., [1] discussed the concept of Tribonacci Product Cordial Labeling. An injective function $\delta : R(G) \rightarrow \{T_1, T_2, \dots, T_m\}$ is said to be Tribonacci product cordial labelling if the induced function $\delta^* : B(G) \rightarrow \{0,1\}$ defined by $\delta^*(r_i r_j) = (\delta(r_i)\delta(r_j)) \pmod{2}$ satisfies the condition $|b_{\delta^*}(0) - b_{\delta^*}(1)| \leq 1$.

A graph which admits Tribonacci Product cordial labelling is called Tribonacci product cordial graph. A Star graph S_m is a complete bipartite graph $K_{1,m}$, where $n + 1$ represents the number of vertices and S_m has m edges.

Double star $DS_{m,m}$ is a tree $K_{1,m,m}$ obtained from the star $K_{1,m}$ by adding a new pendent edge of the existing m pendant vertices. It has $2m + 1$ vertices and $2m$ edges.

The Sun graph of order $2m$ is cycle with edges terminating in a pendent vertex attached to each vertex and it is denoted by SG_m . Vertex set has $R(SG_m) = \{u_1, u_2, u_3, \dots, u_m, r_1, r_2, r_3, \dots, r_m\}$ and edge set has $B(SG_m) = \{u_i r_i \mid i = 1, 2, \dots, m\} \cup \{u_i u_{i+1} \mid i = 1, 2, \dots, m - 1\} \cup \{u_m u_1\}$.

A helm graph H_m , $m \geq 3$, is obtained from a wheel W_m by adjoining a pendant edge at each vertex of the wheel except the center. A flower graph Fl_m , $m \geq 3$, is obtained from a helm H_m by joining each pendent vertex to the central vertex of the helm.

2. MAIN RESULT

In this section we investigate the existence of Tribonacci product Cordial Labeling on Star, Double Star, Sun and Flower graphs.

THEOREM 2.1

Star graph admits Tribonacci product cordial labeling

Proof

From the structure of star graph S_m , It is clear that star has $m + 1$ vertices and m edges.

Define the function $\delta: R \rightarrow \{T_1, T_2, T_3, \dots, T_m\}$ to label the vertices as follows:

For $1 \leq i \leq m + 1$

$$\delta(r_i) = T_i$$

To obtain the edge labels, define the induced function $\delta^*: B \rightarrow \{0,1\}$ given by $\delta^*(r_i r_j) = (\delta(r_i) \delta(r_j)) \pmod{2}$. Thus using the induced function the edges receive the labels as follows:

Case(i): $m = 4n$

For $1 \leq i \leq \frac{m}{4}$

$$(i) \quad \delta^*(r_i r_{4i-2}) = 1$$

$$(ii) \quad \delta^*(r_i r_{4i+1}) = 1$$

$$(iii) \quad \delta^*(r_i r_{4i-1}) = 0$$

$$(iv) \quad \delta^*(r_i r_{4i}) = 0$$

Case(ii): $m = 4n + 2$

For $1 \leq i \leq \frac{m+2}{4}$

$$(i) \quad \delta^*(r_i r_{4i-2}) = 1$$

$$(ii) \quad \delta^*(r_i r_{4i-1}) = 0$$

For $1 \leq i \leq \frac{m-2}{4}$

(i) $\delta^*(r_i r_{4i+1}) = 1$

(ii) $\delta^*(r_i r_{4i}) = 0$

Case(iii): $m = 4n - 1$

For $1 \leq i \leq \frac{m-3}{4}$, $\delta^*(r_i r_{4i+1}) = 1$

For $1 \leq i \leq \frac{m+1}{4}$

(i) $\delta^*(r_i r_{4i-2}) = 1$

(ii) $\delta^*(r_i r_{4i-1}) = 0$

(iii) $\delta^*(r_i r_{4i}) = 0$

Case(iv): $m = 4n + 1$

For $1 \leq i \leq \frac{m+3}{4}$, $\delta^*(r_i r_{4i-2}) = 1$

For, $1 \leq i \leq \frac{m-1}{4}$

(i) $\delta^*(r_i r_{4i+1}) = 1$

(ii) $\delta^*(r_i r_{4i-1}) = 0$

(iii) $\delta^*(r_i r_{4i}) = 0$

Thus the number of edges labelled with 0 and 1 for all the cases areas follows:

Cases	S_m	Lable'0'	Lable'1'
1	$m = 4n$	$\frac{m}{2}$	$\frac{m}{2}$
2	$m = 4n + 2$	$\frac{m}{2}$	$\frac{m}{2}$
3	$m = 4n - 1$	$\frac{m + 1}{2}$	$\frac{m - 1}{2}$
4	$m = 4n + 1$	$\frac{m - 1}{2}$	$\frac{m + 1}{2}$

Hence the condition $|B_{\delta^*}(0) - B_{\delta^*}(1)| \leq 1$ is satisfied. Therefore, the Star graph S_m admits Tribonacci product cordial labeling.

EXAMPLE 2.1:

Tribonacci product cordial labeling for S_4 , S_6 , S_3, S_5 is shown in the figure 2.1.1, 2.1.2, 2.1.3., 2.1.4 respectively.

Figure 2.1.1

Figure 2.1.2

Figure 2.1.3

Figure 2.1.4

THEOREM 2.2:

Double Star graph $DS_{m,m}$ admits Tribonacci product cordial labeling

Proof

From the structure of Double Star graph $DS_{m,m}$, it is clear that $DS_{m,m}$ has $2m + 1$ vertices and $2m$ edges.

Define the function $\delta: R \rightarrow \{T_1, T_2, T_3, \dots, T_m\}$ to label the vertices as follows:

Case(i): $m = 1(mod 2)$

$$\partial(u) = T_1$$

For $1 \leq i \leq \frac{m+1}{2}$

(i) $\delta(r_{2i-1}) = T_{4i-2}$

(ii) $\delta(w_{2i-1}) = T_{4i-1}$

For $1 \leq i \leq \frac{m-1}{2}$

(i) $\delta(r_{2i}) = T_{4i+1}$

(ii) $\delta(w_{2i}) = T_{4i}$

Case(ii): $m = 1(mod 2)$

$$\partial(u) = T_1$$

For $1 \leq i \leq \frac{m}{2}$

(i) $\delta(r_{2i-1}) = T_{4i-2}$

(ii) $\delta(w_{2i-1}) = T_{4i-1}$

$$(iii) \delta(r_{2i}) = T_{4i+1}$$

$$(iv) \delta(w_{2i}) = T_{4i}$$

To obtain the edge labels, define the induced function $\delta^* : B \rightarrow \{0,1\}$ defined by $\delta^*(r_i r_j) = (\delta(r_i)\delta(r_j)) \pmod{2}$. Thus using the induced function the edges receive the labels as follows:

For $1 \leq i \leq m$

$$(i) \delta^*(ur_i) = 1$$

$$(ii) \delta^*(r_i w_i) = 0$$

Hence the condition $|B_{\delta^*}(0) - B_{\delta^*}(1)| \leq 1$ is satisfied.

Therefore, the Double Star graph $DS_{m,m}$ admits Tribonacci product cordial labeling

EXAMPLE 2.2:

Tribonacci product cordial labeling for $DS_{5,5}$ is shown in the figure 2.2.1 respectively.

Figure 2.2.1

THEOREM 2.3:

Sun graph SG_m admits Tribonacci product cordial labeling

Proof

From the structure of Sun graph SG_m , it is clear that SG_m has $2m$ vertices and $2m$ edges.

Define the function $\delta : R \rightarrow \{T_1, T_2, T_3, \dots, T_m\}$ to lable the vertices as follows:

Case(i): $m = 0(mod2)$

For $1 \leq i \leq \frac{m}{2}$

(i) $\delta(u_{2i-1}) = T_{4i-3}$

(ii) $\delta(u_{2i}) = T_{4i-2}$

(iii) $\delta(r_{2i-1}) = T_{4i-1}$

(iv) $\delta(r_{2i}) = T_{4i}$

Case(ii): $m = 1(mod2)$

For $1 \leq i \leq \frac{m+1}{2}$

(i) $\delta(u_i) = T_{4i-3}$

(ii) $\delta\left(u_{\frac{m+2i+1}{2}}\right) = T_{4i-1}$

(i) $\delta(r_i) = T_{4i-2}$

(ii) $\delta\left(r_{\frac{m+2i+1}{2}}\right) = T_{4i}$

To obtain the edge labels, define the induced function $\delta^* : B \rightarrow \{0,1\}$ given by $\delta^*(r_i r_j) = (\delta(r_i)\delta(r_j))(mod2)$. Thus using the induced function the edges receive the labels as follows:

Case(i): $m = 0(mod2)$

(i) $\delta^*(u_1 u_n) = 1$

For $1 \leq i \leq m - 1$

(ii) $\delta^*(u_i u_{i+1}) = 1$

For $1 \leq i \leq m$

(iii) $\delta^*(u_i r_i) = 0$

Case(ii): $m = 1(mod2)$

(i) $\delta^*(u_1 u_n) = 0$

For $m - 1 \leq i \leq 2m - 4$

(ii) $\delta^*(u_i u_{i+1}) = 0$

For $m \leq i \leq 2m - 3$

(iii) $\delta^*(u_i r_i) = 0$

For $1 \leq i \leq m - 1$

(iv) $\delta^*(u_i r_i) = 1$

For $1 \leq i \leq m - 2$

$$(v) \quad \delta^*(u_i u_{i+1}) = 1$$

$$\text{So, } |B_{\delta^*}(0) - B_{\delta^*}(1)| = |m - m| = 0$$

Hence the condition $|B_{\delta^*}(0) - B_{\delta^*}(1)| \leq 1$ is satisfied.

Therefore, the Sun graph SG_m admits Tribonacci product cordial labeling

EXAMPLE 2.3:

Tribonacci product cordial labeling for SG_3 and SG_4 is shown in the figure 2.3.1 and 2.3.2 respectively.

Figure 2.3.1

Figure 2.3.2

THEOREM 2.4

Flower graph Fl_m admits Tribonacci product cordial labeling

Proof

From the structure of Flower graph Fl_m , it is clear that Fl_m has $2m + 1$ vertices and $4m$ edges.

Define the function $\delta: R \rightarrow \{T_1, T_2, T_3, \dots, T_m\}$ to label the vertices as follows:

Case(i): $m \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$

$$(i) \quad \delta(u) = T_1$$

$$\text{For } 1 \leq i \leq \frac{m+1}{2}$$

$$(ii) \quad \delta(r_{2i-1}) = T_{4i-2}$$

$$(iii) \quad \delta(r_{2i}) = T_{4i+1}$$

$$(iv) \quad \delta(w_{2i-1}) = T_{4i-1}$$

$$\text{For } 1 \leq i \leq \frac{m-1}{2}$$

$$(v) \quad \delta(r_{2i}) = T_{4i}$$

Case(ii): $m \equiv 0 \pmod{2}$

$$(i) \quad \delta(u) = T_1$$

$$\text{For } 1 \leq i \leq \frac{m}{2}$$

$$(ii) \quad \delta(r_{2i-1}) = T_{4i-2}$$

$$(iii) \quad \delta(r_{2i}) = T_{4i+1}$$

$$(iv) \quad \delta(w_{2i-1}) = T_{4i-1}$$

$$(v) \quad \delta(r_{2i}) = T_{4i}$$

To obtain the edge labels, define the induced function $\delta^*: B \rightarrow \{0,1\}$ defined by $\delta^*(r_i r_j) = (\delta(r_i)\delta(r_j)) \pmod{2}$. Thus using the induced function the edges receive the labels as follows:

$$(i) \quad \delta^*(r_1 r_n) = 1$$

$$\text{For } 1 \leq i \leq m$$

$$(ii) \quad \delta^*(ur_i) = 1$$

$$(iii) \quad \delta^*(uw_i) = 0$$

$$(iv) \quad \delta^*(r_i w_i) = 0$$

$$\text{For } 1 \leq i \leq m - 1$$

$$(\forall) \quad \delta^*(r_i r_{i+1}) = 1$$

$$\text{So, } |B_{\delta^*}(0) - B_{\delta^*}(1)| = |2m - 2m| = 0$$

Hence the condition $|B_{\delta^*}(0) - B_{\delta^*}(1)| \leq 1$ is satisfied.

Therefore, the Flower graph Fl_m admits Tribonacci product cordial labeling.

EXAMPLE 2.4:

Tribonacci product cordial labeling for Flower graph Fl_m is shown in the figure 2.4.1 and 2.4.2 respectively.

Figure 2.4.1

Figure 2.4.2

CONCLUSION

This paper, we have confirmed the existence of Tribonacci Product Cordial Labeling for Star, Double star, Sun and Flower graphs.

References

1. Bala S, Suganya V, Thirusangu. K, Cordial labeling on Extended Triplicated Complete Bipartite Graph, IPL Journal of Management, Vol 14, NO 18, July-December2024, ISSN:2249-9040.
2. Boulet R, Spectral Characterization of Sun graphs and broken sun graphs, Discrete Math.Therr.Compt.Sci.,11,(2009) 149-160.
3. Cahit.I, Cordial graphs; a weaker version of graceful and harmonious graphs, Ars Combin, 23 (1987), 201-207.
4. Jeyanthi P and Jeya Daisy K, Z_k -Magic Labeling of Some Families of Graphs, Journal of Algorithms and Computation 50 issue 2, December 2018, PP.1 – 12.
5. Marr A M and Wallis WD, Magic Graphs New York: Springer Science & Business Media,2013.
6. Maulidia A R and Purwanto, Elegant labeling of sun graphs and helm graphs, Journal of Physics, Conf. Ser. 1872 012008 ,ISSN:1742-6596,2020.
7. Mitra S and Bhoumik S, Fibonacci Cordial Labeling of Some Special Families of Graphs, Annals of Pure and Applied Mathematics,21(2020),135-140.
8. Rosa A H and Ghodasara G V, Fibonacci cordial labeling of some special Graphs, Annais of pure and Applied Mthematics Vol, 11, No,1,2016,133-144,ISSN-2279-087X(P), 2279-0888(online),Published on 29 February 2016.
9. Sarbari Mitra, Soumya Bhoumik, Tribonacci Cordial Labeling of Graphs, Journal of Applied Mathematics and physics,2022,10,1394-1402.
10. Shiu, W.C. and Low, R.M. Z_k -magic labeling of fans and wheels with magic-valuezero, Australas. J. Combin., 45 (2009), 309–316.
11. Sundaram M,Ponraj R, and Somasundaram S, product cordial labelling of graphs, Bulletin of pure and Applied Science, Vol.23E(NO.1)2004.
12. Tessymol Abraham, Shiny Jose, Fibonacci Product Cordial Labeling, JETIR January 2019,Volume 6,Issue 1,ISSN-2349-5162.
13. Ulaganathan P P, Selvam B, Vijaya kumar P, Signed Product Cordial labeling in duplicate graphs of Bistar, Double Star and Triangular Ladder Graph, International Journal of Mathematics Trends and Technology (IJMTT) ,Volume 33 Number 1- May 2016. ISSN: 2231-5373 .<http://www.ijmtjournal.org>.
14. Venkatachalam M, Vernold Vivin J and Kaliraj K, armonious Colouring on double star graph families, Tamkang Journal of Mathematics, Vol. 43, No. 2, 153 – 158.
15. zero, Australas. J. Combin., 45 (2009), 309–316.